

IMPACT OF THE EDUCATIONAL SYSTEM OF THE ORGANIZATION OF ENGLISH LANGUAGE TO PRIMARY CLASS STUDENTS ON THE BASE OF MODERN TECHNOLOGIES

*I. Komolova*¹

Abstract:

Information technologies have affected every aspect of human activity and have a potential role to play in the field of education and training, specially, in distance education to transform it into an innovative form of experience. The need of new technologies in teaching learning process grows stronger and faster. The information age becomes an era of knowledge providing sound and unmatched feasibility for discovery, exchange of information, communication and exploration to strengthen the teaching learning process.

Information technologies help in promoting opportunities of knowledge sharing throughout the world. These can help the teachers and students having up-to-date information and knowledge.

Method: This article discusses the influence of modern information technologies on the educational system of teaching English to elementary school students.

Result: It is important to teach children with the help of technologies that meet the needs of different times. However, children quickly get bored with the sameness and lose interest in the lesson. While reading the article, there is an opportunity to learn about the organization of the lesson with the help of information technologies.

Key words: new words, flashcards, visual tools, computer, information technology tools, projector, discs, electronic textbooks.

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Introduction: Everyone knows that today's children are growing up in the age of technology. They have the opportunity to use modern information technologies at every step. However, in our country, special attention is paid to public education, as well as to the acquisition of in-depth knowledge of the young generation. With the honor of our country's president, special attention is paid to the quality of education in schools. The decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On approval of the concept of development of the system of public education of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030" was signed. [John Adams, 2017;1]

According to the decree, to determine the priorities for the systematic reform of general secondary and extracurricular education in the Republic of Uzbekistan, to raise the moral, moral and intellectual development of the young generation to a new level in terms of quality, In order to introduce innovative forms and methods of

¹ *Komolova Iqbol Adhamovna, PhD student, Samarkand State University named after Sharof Rashidov*

education into the educational process, the concept of developing the public education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030 is approved. [Xalq so'zi 2012 ; 2]

In fact, the role of modern pedagogical technologies and information and communication tools in improving the quality and efficiency of education, in the purposeful organization of game-type lessons that interest students is very large. is becoming an integral part of the educational process. In order to teach English to young people through the computer, first of all, the teacher himself must be able to use computer technologies at a professional level. it also includes the ability to organize new educational programs based on it. In order to become a pedagogue of this level, every foreign language teacher needs to work more on himself in the field of modern technologies. Computer-based English language teaching has several advantages compared to traditional teaching methods. First of all, a computer-based English language learner has four areas of language skills (speaking, listening, writing, and reading). will be able to test their skills. Currently, this is possible with the help of advanced programs. It is only necessary to be able to properly direct the student to this method of education. In addition, it has been proven that every rule, every word, every unit of concept taught in the teaching of foreign languages with the help of a computer is better retained in the student's memory. [J.Jalolov-2022; 3] Naturally, the computer's rich graphic capabilities, the ability to deliver situational information in the form of voice, text, images and video make teaching foreign languages through the computer one of the most effective methods. Basically, it is appropriate to use Word and Power Point programs to explain current topics. Because I think that students will understand much easier if the topic is explained using table views through the Word program. In Power Point, students can be more involved in the topic by showing these topics in audio, picture and video formats.

We can mention the following advantages of using information technologies in primary school classes;

- You will make it possible to present the educational material in a more understandable and comprehensible way.

- Contribute to the implementation of developmental education, problem-dialogic approach, allows to organize research activities in the classroom.

- Allow for a differentiated approach to learning.

- The use of computer tests and test game works in the lesson allows the teacher to have an objective idea of the mastery of the studied material in a short time and to correct it in time. The high emotional level of primary school students is significantly limited by the strict framework of the educational process. Lessons allow to relieve high emotional tension and revive the learning process. The computer is also a powerful stimulus for children's creativity, including the youngest or disabled children. The screen attracts attention, which we sometimes do not get when working with the front of the classroom. It is possible to quickly make changes in the deformed text on the screen, to turn contradictory sentences into a coherent text. In primary classes, information technologies are used at all stages of the lesson. [N.To'xtasinova-2021; 4]

The importance of information technology in Olympiads, extracurricular activities, explaining new material, correcting, repeating, controlling is incomparable.

The Internet and information technology tools provide students with the latest relevant information at their own pace and. They can form a virtual community of learners globally. Effectiveness, accessibility, and flexibility of choice due to the high cost of information and communication technologies in educational organizations, particularly computers, the World Wide Web, teleconferencing, and educational television.

Students use information technology for the following purposes:

1. Participate in a media revolution that will profoundly affect their way of thinking;

Information technology and its use;

2. Improvement of learning methods in new educational methods;

3. To expand the ability and skills to apply their knowledge in a real situation;

4. Working in groups for cooperation and cooperative learning;

5. Develop habits of self-study at one's own pace and time;

6. Learn with the teacher rather than the teacher;[Pratova G.- 2021;5]

7. Development of inquiry-learning habits;

8. Use the right information at the right time to achieve the right goal;

9. Review and study qualitative data;

10. Sharing learning experiences and information with other students and teachers living anywhere in the world;

Information technology supports the learning process of students

active participation on the one hand, and helping teachers on the other.

Teachers use information technology for the following purposes:

[Abdug'afurovich R.- 2022;6]

1. Present the material in a more interesting and attractive way.

2. Guiding and assisting students in finding quality material.

3. Make the most of your time.

4. Mentoring children.

5. Give individual instruction.

6. Guide students to cooperative and collaborative learning events.

7. Situations where learning material is prepared for students rather than traditional teaching.

8. Diagnosing students' learning problems and helping to solve them.

9. Solving students' educational problems. [Iriskulov A. 2014;7]

In our country, many measures are being taken to strengthen the knowledge of elementary school students so that they can master their basic knowledge thoroughly. School teachers organize lessons with the help of modern technologies.

Summary. Information technology is the result of knowledge explosion. Various

Hardware and software technologies and helps to organize the educational process in a qualitative manner. IT students can now participate in learning communities around the world. They are independent and free to choose their own programs. The importance of the pedagogue and technology in learning and resource use, joint learning, and information sharing is considered high.

Information technology facilitates the educational process and helps to organize it more effectively. In the same way, the role of the teacher in the new

conditions is different, compared to the traditional system, we can see a higher quality of education and the course of the lesson. In lessons organized through information technologies, the technology mainly leads the lesson, and the teacher gives guidance and direction. Because today's children are growing up with modern technologies.

In short, information technology reorganizes the teaching process and meets international standards.

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